

Teaching English to young children through different things

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Annotation: In this article, different methods of teaching English and foreign languages to children at school, and simplification of language learning with the help of different things are discussed.

Key words: teaching, school, foreign language, knowledge.

Our country has been paying attention to a lot of areas in the last 10 years. Including the Presidential Decree "On further improvement of the system of foreign language learning" adopted on December 10, 2012, as well as the study of foreign languages in the primary classes of general education schools starting from the 2013-2014 school year. the introduction of teaching is a clear example of it. Today, not only school, secondary and higher education students, but also MTM trainees, as well as employees working in various fields, learn a foreign language, especially English. The main reason for this is economic science and cultural learning the languages of developed countries is the main factor in acquiring the achievements of world science and development. Language learning is definitely divided into young periods, for example, according to statistical data, children learn a foreign language faster and easier than adults. The fact that the passion is stronger than that of adults is that children have more time ng is a clear example. It should not be forgotten that 5-8-year-old children do not understand the essence of information, but memorize it mechanically. Therefore, it is certainly not without benefits to start teaching language to elementary school students with grammatical rules. Otherwise, children will not learn the language Therefore, teaching young children a foreign language is a very difficult and responsible task. To make teaching a foreign language meaningful and effective to young children, the following methods can be used.

- First of all, it is an effective way for children to learn the English alphabet in the form of songs rather than just memorizing it. In addition, games based on physical

and mental movements, songs, movies and cartoons, as well as picture dictionaries are examples of this. In young children, we can observe that it is easier for them to learn by seeing, hearing and repeating. In this respect, they differ from adults. It is worth noting one more thing that the teacher can create an atmosphere in the classroom, the students' interest in the subject and their worldview will increase. For example, if the topic is about wild animals, even if the teacher pastes pictures of animals on the board or brings his figurines, the children will have an idea about it. and their vocabulary increases.

-Practical training (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers).

This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "A pedagogue who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should use the child's sensory organs as much as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscles, and even if possible should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering".

For example: when a student tastes an apple, the teacher should inform about its color, whether it is red or green, taste sweet or sour, smell, and give other children information about that fruit. If the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the time when he ate the fruit. This method ensures that the student will retain the information in his memory for a long time.

- Through visual aids, posters, books.

- It is not without benefit to teach by tying things to things that are visible and often used in everyday life.

We know that children are curious and they quickly get bored of the same things. For this reason, it requires great skill and creativity from the teacher to interest and attract the child.

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should not be done as an obligation, but as an interesting activity, using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr

Farabi. He also knew many foreign languages perfectly, was able to speak and create in these languages with ease. knows".

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